

Synthesis and characterization of Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 2,15-dimethyl-3,16-diethyl/propyl/phenyl-1,4,14,17-tetraazacyclohexacos-1,3,14,16-tetraene

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Abstract : 2+2 Cyclocondensation reactions of 1,9-diaminononane with α -diketones viz. 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione in the presence of metal ions as templates have afforded hexacoordinated complexes of the general formula $[MLX_2]$ (where M = Mg, Ca, Sr or Ba; L = N_4 macrocycle having 26-membered ring and X = Cl or NCS). The resulting macrocyclic complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductance measurements and IR and 1H NMR spectra.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, alkaline earth metal complexes, IR spectra, 1H NMR spectra.

Introduction

A large number of azamacrocycles and their complexes have been synthesized during the recent years due to their close resemblance with biological systems. Such syntheses have generally been accomplished using transition metal ions as templates in the condensation reactions of diamines with α - or β -diketones¹. However, alkaline earth metal ions have also been used as templates for the synthesis of azamacrocyclic complexes. Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 18- and 24-membered azamacrocycles derived from 2,6-diformyl- or 2,6-diacetylpyridine have been reported². Earlier, alkaline earth metal complexes of 18-membered tetraazamacrocycles derived from (2+2) cyclocondensation of α -diketones and 1,5-diaminopentane have been reported from our laboratories³. In the present paper Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 26-membered tetraazamacrocycles derived from 1,9-diaminononane and α -diketones such as 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione are described.

Results and discussion

2+2 Cyclocondensation of 1,9-diaminononane and α -diketones such as 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione in the presence of metal nitrates or chlorides has resulted in the formation of M^{II} complexes (I) of 26-membered tetraazamacrocycles 2,15-

dimethyl-3,16-diethyl/propyl/phenyl-1,4,14,17-tetraazacyclohexacos-1,3,14,16-tetraene according to Scheme 1 in 23–78% yield.

(I)

M	X	R ¹	R ²
Mg	Cl	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅ , C ₃ H ₇ , C ₆ H ₅
Ca	NCS	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅ , C ₃ H ₇ , C ₆ H ₅
Sr	NCS	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅ , C ₃ H ₇
Ba	NCS	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅ , C ₃ H ₇

Scheme 1. Synthesis of alkaline earth metal complexes of tetraazamacrocycles.

The resulting macrocyclic complexes have 12-membered chelate rings which are not improbable due to the flexibility of the ring and have been reported earlier in case of the complexes of long chain flexible bidentate ligands such as Co^{III} complexes of diaminoalkanes $\text{H}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{NH}_2$ ($n = 2-14$)⁴ and platinum and palladium complexes of diphosphines $\text{Bu}^t_2\text{P}(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{PBu}^t_2$ ($n = 9, 10$ or 12)⁵. Moreover, such chelate rings would be more stable in metal complexes of macrocyclic ligands since macrocyclic complexes are often stabilized to a greater extent by the macrocyclic effect 'multiple juxtapositional fixedness'⁶.

These complexes are isolated as yellow or brown solids which decompose on heating. They are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether, nitromethane and *n*-hexane but are soluble in DMSO. Their analyses and characteristics are given in Table 1. Molar conductances of the complexes are generally low (Table 1) supporting their non-electrolytic behaviour. Thus the chloro or thiocyanato groups are coordinated to the metal atom indicating hexacoordinated environment around the metal atom. However, the higher values of conductances in some

cases may be due to the replacement of weakly coordinated chloro or thiocyanato groups by the solvent molecules.

Infrared spectra :

All the complexes exhibit a strong band at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is assigned to the coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and no absorption band is observed at 1700 or $3200-3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which shows the absence of unreacted $\text{C}=\text{O}$ or NH_2 groups. Thus the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ groups of α -diketones and NH_2 groups of the diamine have condensed to give $\text{C}=\text{N}$ linkage. Similar observations have been made by other workers in case of metal complexes of other macrocycles⁷. A broad band at $\sim 550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu\text{M}-\text{N}$ ⁸. The bands at $2050-2070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to N-bonded thiocyanato group in the complexes of Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} . Lowering of this frequency as compared to that reported for free thiocyanate (2100 cm^{-1}) supports the coordination of thiocyanate to the metal atom. Fenton and Cook⁹ have reported N-bonded thiocyanate stretching frequencies at $2063, 2073$ and 2081 cm^{-1} in Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes respectively of the macrocycle 3,15,21-triaza-6,9,12-trioxabicyclo[15.3.1]heneicosa-1(21),2,5,17,19-pentaene.

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of M^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles

Complex	Colour and temp. of decomp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$)
		M	N	Cl	
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Et}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{MgCl}_2]$	Mustard yellow (200)	4.64 (4.66)	10.51 (10.71)	13.61 (13.59)	62
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Pr}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{MgCl}_2]$	Yellow (210)	4.37 (4.27)	9.87 (9.86)	12.43 (12.48)	78
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{MgCl}_2]$	Yellow (173)	3.91 (3.82)	8.74 (8.80)	11.04 (11.14)	86
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Et}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ca}(\text{NCS})_2]$	Yellow (200)	6.57 (6.66)	9.30 (9.32)	-	33
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Pr}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ca}(\text{NCS})_2]$	Light yellow (200)	6.20 (6.37)	8.88 (8.90)	-	161
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Ph}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ca}(\text{NCS})_2]$	Yellow (205)	5.73 (5.74)	8.01 (8.03)	-	166
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Et}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Sr}(\text{NCS})_2]$	Brown (140)	13.50 (13.51)	8.60 (8.63)	-	21
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Pr}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Sr}(\text{NCS})_2]$	Light yellow (210)	12.88 (12.95)	8.25 (8.28)	-	27
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Et}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ba}(\text{NCS})_2]$	Brown (190)	19.62 (19.65)	7.97 (8.02)	-	15
$[(\text{Me}_2\text{Pr}_2[26]\text{tetraeneN}_4)\text{Ba}(\text{NCS})_2]$	Brown (215)	18.87 (18.89)	7.68 (7.71)	-	21

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra :

¹H NMR spectra of Mg^{II} complexes have been recorded and the δ values (ppm) for different protons are given in Table 2. In free 1,9-diaminononane the α -CH₂ protons appear as a triplet at δ 2.68 ppm, while β and other CH₂ protons appear as a quintet at δ 1.31 ppm. In

ppm while the CH₂^b protons of the ethyl group appear as a multiplet at δ 2.26 ppm. In free 2,3-pentanedione (CH₃^cCOCOCH₂^bCH₃^a) the CH₃^c protons give a singlet at δ 2.35 ppm, CH₃^a protons exhibit a triplet at δ 1.06 ppm, while CH₂^b protons give a quartet at δ 2.74 ppm. The high field shifting of CH₃^c protons of the methyl

Table 2. ¹H NMR chemical shifts (δ , ppm) of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes

Complex	Amine residue		Ketone residue	
	α -CH ₂	β -CH ₂	CH ₃ ^{a,c}	CH ₂ ^b
[(Me ₂ Et ₂ [26]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	2.74t	1.30b	0.81t	2.26m
[(Me ₂ Pr ₂ [26]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	2.74t	1.30b	0.84t	2.35m

t = triplet, m = multiplet, b = broad.

KIM (II) the α -CH₂ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.64 ppm and β -CH₂ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm¹⁰. This downfield shift as compared to the protons of free diamine is due to deshielding by π -electrons of C=N bond. The free macrocycles, though not isolated, would have exhibited these resonances at almost similar positions as in KIM. In the macrocyclic complexes of Mg^{II}, α -CH₂ protons exhibit a triplet at δ 2.74 ppm (*J* 6–7 Hz) and β and other methylene protons exhibit a broad peak at δ 1.30 ppm. Upfield shift of α - and β -CH₂ protons in these complexes as compared to KIM supports the coordination of nitrogen to the metal atom in these macrocyclic complexes.

KIM (II)

Methyl and methylene protons of the ketone residue of macrocyclic complexes exhibit very weak signals. In the Mg^{II} complex (III) of the macrocycle derived from 2,3-pentanedione the CH₃ protons give a triplet at δ 0.81

(III)

group and CH₂^b protons of ethyl group in the complexes confirms the coordination of nitrogen of the macrocycle to the metal atom. However, the CH₃^a protons of ethyl group are very slightly shifted as these are away from the C=N group and are not affected much by coordination.

In the Mg^{II} complex of the macrocycle derived from 2,3-hexanedione the peaks of the protons of the ketone residue are almost at the same positions as in the complex of macrocycle derived from 2,3-pentanedione.

Experimental**Materials :**

2,3-Pentanedione (Fluka), 2,3-hexanedione (Aldrich), 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione (Aldrich) and 1,9-diaminononane (Aldrich) were used as supplied.

MgCl₂·6H₂O (BDH), Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (BDH), SrCl₂·6H₂O (E. Merck) and BaCl₂·2H₂O (Glaxo) were of AR grade. Methanol, ethanol and butanol were distilled before use.

Analytical methods and physical measurements :

Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically using EDTA, barium gravimetrically as barium sulphate, nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method and chlorine gravimetrically as AgCl. IR spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer as KBr pellets in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ on a Zeol FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as reference. Conductances were measured in DMSO using a Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-304.

Synthesis of Mg^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles :

To the butanolic solution of MgCl₂·6H₂O (2.8 mmol in ~20 ml), a butanolic solution of 2,3-pentanedione (5.6 mmol in 10 ml) was added. Then a butanolic solution of 1,9-diaminononane (5.6 mmol in 10 ml) was added to this with continuous stirring. The contents were stirred for ~6 h. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reactions of MgCl₂·6H₂O were carried out with 1,9-diaminononane and 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione to afford Mg^{II} complexes of 26-membered tetraazamacrocycles.

Synthesis of Ca^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles :

To the butanolic solution of Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (1.7 mmol in ~20 ml), a butanolic solution of 2,3-pentanedione (3.4 mmol in 10 ml) was added. To this, a butanolic solution of 1,9-diaminononane (3.4 mmol in 10 ml) was added with continuous stirring. As no solid appeared, a butanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (3.4 mmol) was added. Stirring was continued for ~6 h maintaining the temperature 60°C throughout the reaction. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similar reactions of Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O with 1,9-diaminononane and 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione were carried out to afford corresponding Ca^{II} complexes of 26-membered tetraazamacrocycles.

Synthesis of Sr^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles :

To the methanolic solution of SrCl₂·6H₂O (1.7 mmol in ~20 ml), a methanolic solution of 2,3-pentanedione (3.4 mmol in 10 ml) was added. To this 1,9-diaminononane (3.4 mmol in 10 ml methanol) was added drop by drop with constant stirring. As no solid appeared, a methanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (3.4 mmol) was added with continuous stirring. Stirring was continued for ~10 h. The solid product was filtered, washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reaction of SrCl₂·6H₂O was carried out with 1,9-diaminononane and 2,3-hexanedione and Sr^{II} complex of corresponding 26-membered tetraazamacrocycle was isolated.

Synthesis of Ba^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles :

BaCl₂·2H₂O (2.1 mmol) was dissolved in ethanol-water (1 : 1, 20 ml) and an ethanolic solution of 2,3-pentanedione (4.2 mmol in 10 ml) was added. Then ethanolic solution of 1,9-diaminononane (4.2 mmol in 10 ml) was added drop by drop with continuous stirring. As no solid appeared ethanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (4.2 mmol) was added. Stirring was continued for 10 h and the solid obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reaction of BaCl₂·2H₂O with 1,9-diaminononane and 2,3-hexanedione was carried out and Ba^{II} complex of the corresponding 26-membered tetraazamacrocycle was isolated.

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Prasad *et al.* : Synthesis and characterization of Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes *etc.*

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